

Title: Numeric Treatment of the 3D images applied on the material of tire (Electron Tomography)

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INTRODUCTION:

High-resolution electron tomography is a powerful imaging technique that enables three-dimensional analysis of material at the nanometer scale.

AIM:

The objective of this imaging technique is the reconstruction of a volume in 3D and to perform the quantitative analysis of the Nano scale silica composites present in the tire sample.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials used in this process:

- 1) Nano Sample of tire
- 2) Dual Beam Microscope
- 3) Transmission Electron Microscope
- 4) Inspect 3D and Fiji Software

In the first step of this, the objective is to propose some reconstruction algorithms leading to decrease in the computation time. Visualizing and analyzing the nano-composite sample requires its accurate segmentation from the series of projected images obtained through electron microscope. As a manual process this requires a great amount of expert knowledge, whilst also very tedious and time consuming, taking on lot of days to segment all the slices in a full data set. In the second step we have proposed a method of segmentation which reduce the total time of the segmentation from around four-five days to a single day taking into account other required manual process that are difficult to automate. Consequently, this has a large impact on the throughput of data from the electron microscope to the analyst requiring the data to lead their research. Considering, how important the dispersion of silica is in the tire sample for computing the performance of the tire therefore, in the third step, we present a method to measure the silica dispersion in the rubber compound. As expected, silica with the larger fraction volume has lower characteristic spacing compared to less fraction volume of silica. The work represents a huge step towards developing and testing the protocol related to the construction, acquisition, reconstruction, segmentation and extraction of 3D information's from the tire sample.

RESULTS:

In this we were mainly interested in knowing the performance of tire depending upon the distribution and distance between the two atoms. The results obtained were the nano scale sample of tire in the cylindrical format; which were further segmented and analyzed to obtain the best specimen. The filtered and segmented output was further percolated to know the character spacing between the elements and that spacing tell us about the characteristic of tire.

CONCLUSIONS:

This paper consisted of two parts: the 1st part focused on studying and participating in the construction of the cylindrical specimen and acquisition of the image developed through the collaboration between the Michelin group and Cambridge University. Acquisition of the images by the transmission electron microscope defines forward problem.

In the second part, various reconstruction approach being used to reconstruct the 3D volume. Among various reconstructions algorithm best algorithm is utilized for the volume reconstruction after comparing various parameters. After reconstruction, various image processing techniques have been used to improve the image quality.

The main objective of finding the filter with suitable parameter is to reduce the noise and the blurring effect before segmentation. Various filters have been tested and the best among all have been found. Segmentation was performed to separate the various different materials in the tire material. For image segmentation, many approaches have been proposed but there are two techniques which seem to be best in the material science.

Result of the quantitative analysis depends on the accuracy of the segmentation, so we proposed two methods of segmentation. The objective of both methods is to segment the different materials of the tire sample. Trainable Weka-segmentation takes four-five days whereas the region based segmentation takes one day and seems to give accurate results.

Evaluation of the dispersion of the silica in a filler content system is analyzed by the method developed by post doctorate. This method allows us to calculate the characteristic spacing of the nanocomposites silica particle in the sample. At the same time this measurement helps to justify the dynamic behavior of the compounds.

Thanks to this project, we reach the certain conclusions:

1. 3D-TEM is a very promising new technique for the characterization of material at nano scale.
2. Dispersion of silica is better when the silica distribution is uniform, with less silica agglomerates. As expected, smaller the average size of the aggregates, better the dispersion, even if the aggregates considered here are dense areas (agglomerates) within a continuous matrix (iso silica).
3. Characteristic spacing decreases when the fraction of the silica volume increases.
4. When the silica is irregularly distributes in the tire material, and then the characteristic spacing between the aggregates of silica may be less compared to when they are regularly distributed at iso-volumic fraction of silica.
5. Nanometer scale resolution in three dimensions.

During the master thesis, we performed the percolation test by setting the filter of 4000 voxels (correspond to particle diameter of 11 nm) to eliminate the effect of artifacts which seems to be little bit larger (normally it is 375-450 voxels) that why, we did not have the smooth curve which was expected. This whole process from the construction of the cylindrical sample with the focused ion beam till performing the analysis (percolation curve) takes 2.5 days for one data compare to 7 days which was needed before this master thesis.

KEYWORDS:

Electron Microscope, Transmission Electron microscope, Fiji, Segmentation, Inspect 3D, Data Acquisition, Alignment and reconstruction

BIOGRAPHY:

Naveen Rathi has completed his masters at the age of 24 years from Ecole Centrale de Nantes, France in Automatic, robotic and applied numeric and Bachelors studies from Birla Institute, Pilani, India. He did his Masters internship in Technological Center of Michelin, Clermont Ferrand, France. He did his bibliographic report on Microwave tomography. He has vast interest in the field of tomography 3D, signal and image processing, nano-particles.